

Large Eddy Simulation of Complex Flow in Combustion Chamber and Residence Time Distribution Calculation

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Abstract:

Large-eddy-simulations (LES) calculations are carried out using the open source software OpenFOAM system for non-reactive gas-phase flow in an oxy-fuel combustion system, which features a complex generic labor-scaled swirled flow combustor, in order to evaluate the residence time distribution (RTD) for a fluid element, which can be influenced by microscopic gas phase induced by turbulence and molecular mixing process. For the reason to predict the influence of the flow and to capture the tracer concentration evolution, different wall-adapted large eddy simulation modelling are used in this study. The first order statistics of the simulation (LES) are compared with experimental data at specific heights and the calculated residence time distribution is analyzed and compared as well to experimental results which presented a good parameter to characterize the reactor and to successfully predict the tracer concentration distribution at the burner outlet.

Keywords: LES, Residence time distribution, swirled burner

1 Introduction

The modern industrialized world is mainly dependent on the combustion of fossil fuels to satisfy its demand of energy. According to the statistical review of world energy; [1] more than 80% of the global demand of primary energy is still generated using combustion of fossil fuels that also includes natural gas. Based on the present rate of energy consumption, International Energy Agency (IEA); [2] has predicted that energy demand may get doubled in the next two decades. Even though there is strong development towards the usage of renewable energy to phase out traditional energy, most of the energy production will still be continued by combustion of fossil fuels. However, the carbon dioxide and pollutants present several undesired consequences such as global rise in temperature and the air quality deterioration due fossil-fuel combustion during energy production.

To face these problems, the modern combustion research faces two main challenges; the optimization of the combustion efficiency and the reduction of the pollutants following the new emission standards [3] and for this reason many technologies are proposed recently to capture undesirable carbon dioxide, in particular, oxy-fuel combustion which is more favorable in energetic point of view and with less expensive options, (Chen et al.[2012]) [4]. However, the design and the optimization of the modern devices requires a good understanding of many complex physical processes such as the heat and mass transfer, the turbulent-unsteady fluid flow, the efficiency, and different interacted processes. This contributes on increasing the use of computational methodology for more details into the chemical and physical phenomenon during combustion and the emission controlling processes.

The experimental investigations have been used widely to better understand this complex combustion phenomena and to carry out design analysis of adopted systems, however it is often extremely expensive, encounters measurement limitations due to inaccessibility of some conditions (very high pressure and temperature) and need longer development timeline. The numerical studies, based on the computational Fluid dynamics (CFD) offers a great alternative potential in these aspects as it requires relatively very low cost and shorter development phase. Once the CFD methodology has been adequately validated with experimental data, it can be used not only to carry out parametric design analysis to reach best possible configurations but also that may underline more information for pollutant-emissions production and chemical-physical interactions [(Chen et al. [2012]) [4]. The interaction between the turbulence and combustion ensues in broad ranges of time and length scales that need to be considered while carrying out numerical modeling and simulation. In this perspective, direct numerical simulation (DNS) is one of the CFD numerical methodology where the Navier–Stokes equations are numerically solved without any turbulence model. This means the whole range of spatial and temporal scales of the turbulence are resolved, and for that, it requires very fine mesh volume and extremely small time step which is not feasible for complex configurations.

Another CFD methodology commonly used is RANS (Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes), this method is limited in term of resolving flow field due to a complete modeling of the turbulent energy spectrum and the transient mixing and combustion processes cannot be represented adequately in order to capture the intrinsically

unsteady phenomena in such systems (e.g. Chen et al. [2012], Toporov et al. [2008] [5], Wang et al. [1988] [6] therefore it is still in practice only for most of industrial application where small scale need not to be resolved. The large Eddy Simulations (LES), considered as a compromise between DNS and RANS, are frequently applied, since they provides temporal flow information that can be very interesting in designing or optimization of combustion related devices not only in research field, but also for industrial interest, as reported by Janicka and Sadiki [2005] [7], Dandois et al. [2006] [8], Pitsch [2006] [9]. Many Large Eddy Simulation studies were established to investigate different thermo-chemical aspects of oxy-fuel combustion as presented in Edge et al. [2011] [10], see also Franchetti et al. [2013] [11], Watanabe et al. [2015] [12], but few of them were addressing to study the residence time of fluid particles in such devices.

In this paper, we attempt to numerically study the behavior of a passive tracer presenting the fluid elements propagating in the oxy-fuel chamber in order to evaluate the residence time distribution (RTD) to make predictions of exit concentrations. The RTD which is defined as the average time spent in a bounded burner, can be evaluated from the exit response of this passive tracer which is issued at the inlet as a pulse or step function; Samim et al [13].

CFD simulations are carried out in this study to simulate single-phase incompressible flow in cold condition using different Large Eddy Simulation modelling to evaluate the RTD of fuel particles. The different LES models are well adapted since the studied chamber is defined as bounded burner. Only the non-reactive case is handled to appraise the RTD in order to define mixing characteristics of the burner for the next step of the study which is the reactive case.

2 Numerical modelling

In the present study, LES for an incompressible constant density fluid was investigated to evaluate at the end the RTD using exit concentrations. For these reasons, and as presented in Figure.1 and Figure.2, a block-structured mesh was generated using the ICEM CFD tool, and for the simulation, the standard solver PimpleFoam of the CFD open-source code OpenFOAM version 2.4.0 has been used where a merged PISO-SIMPLE algorithm is applied for coupling velocity and pressure. For the discretisation of the fluid flow equations in the computational space; the finite volume method was adapted. As the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy (CFL) numbers should be below 0.8, the simulation's time step was set to about 10^{-5} . Different discretization procedure and the numerical schemes for convection and diffusion terms were applied and the reader is referred to the OpenFOAM programmer's guide (Greenshields [2015]) [14] which provides more details of algebraic methods.

Based on the experimental data, the initial and boundary conditions of the numerical simulations are presented in Tab. 1

2.1 Residence Time Distribution RTD

The residence-time distribution (RTD) of a reactor is a characteristic of the mixing that occurs in the chemical reactor, so the idea behind evaluating this parameter was proposed in order to characterize the mixing patterns of these particular systems and analyse their performances, in particular, the performance of oxy-fuel combustors. For the combustor under study is considered as non ideal reactor. The RTD measurements can be determined experimentally by injecting an inert chemical element called a tracer, into the reactor, as shown in Figure.3, at some time (t_0) and then measuring the tracer concentration, in particular at the exit of the reactor. The two most used methods of injection are pulse input and step input as illustrated in Figure.4.

The species injected in the burner should be nonreactive species in order to be easily detectable, generally colored and radioactive materials along with inert gases, also should have physical properties similar to those of the reacting mixture and be completely soluble in the mixture [15]. The mean residence time distribution is determined following this expression:

$$t_m = \tau = \int_0^{\infty} tE(t). dt$$

$$\text{Where } E(t) = \frac{c(t)}{\int_0^{\infty} c(t).dt} \quad \text{and} \quad \int_t^{\infty} E(t). dt = \left[\begin{array}{l} \text{Fraction of effluent} \\ \text{that has been in} \\ \text{the reactor for less} \\ \text{than time } t \end{array} \right] = F(t)$$

In equations above, The quantity E(t) is called the residence-time distribution function, which describes in a quantitative manner how much time different the elements of a fluid have spent in the reactor. However, F(t) presents the cumulative distribution function.

2.2 Large Eddy Simulation

The passive tracer propagation from the inlet to the outlet of the burner influenced is studied based on the unsteady LES of a turbulent single- phase flow in order to predict the residence time distribution by solving a transport equation for the tracer species. As mentioned in the introduction, 4 different LES modelling was applied in the current work which will be explained in details in the next parts of this paper.

2.1.1. Filtered governing equations

When dealing with turbulent flow, a suitable filtering method must be followed where it derives a filtered solution by replacing actual flow parameter values with a filtered values and fluctuation part. The filtered conservation equations for mass and momentum reads:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (\bar{u}_i \bar{u}_j)}{\partial x_j} = - \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\nu \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \bar{u}_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \right) - \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}^{sgs}}{\partial x_j} \quad (2)$$

Where \bar{u}_i is the filtered velocity component in the x_i direction, \bar{p} is the filtered pressure, ν is the kinematic viscosity, τ_{ij}^{sgs} is the SGS stress tensor which will be modelled while solving the filtered equations. Generally it is calculated using the Boussinesq hypothesis, which requires the calculation of the turbulent viscosity and turbulence kinetic energy.

The SGS stress tensor reads:

$$\tau_{ij}^{sgs} = \frac{2}{3} k^{sgs} \sigma_{ij} - \nu_t \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \bar{u}_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \quad (3)$$

Where k^{sgs} is the SGS kinetic energy which is expressed as following in the modified filtered pressure.

$\bar{P} = \bar{p} + \frac{2}{3} k^{sgs}$. If we replace the modified filtered pressure and the isotropic part of the SGS stress tensor we will have a new form of the filtered momentum equation as below:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (\bar{u}_i \bar{u}_j)}{\partial x_j} = - \frac{\partial \bar{P}}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left((\nu + \nu_t) \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \bar{u}_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \right) \quad (4)$$

The reader can referred to Samim et al 2016 [13] for more details about the closure of the filtered momentum and the LES quality assessment. To appraise the residence time distribution while analyzing the concentration of the tracer at the exit, the passive scalar will be presented by the filtered transport equation described below:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\phi}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (\bar{u}_i \bar{\phi})}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\left(\frac{\nu}{Sc} + \frac{\nu_t}{Sc_t} \right) \frac{\partial \bar{\phi}}{\partial x_i} \right) \quad (5)$$

Where ϕ presents the passive scalar, Sc and Sc_t are the laminar and turbulent Schmidt numbers, both are normally constant in a turbulent computation.

To solve the different equations described above, the Sub Grid Scale based on eddy viscosity ν_t are used in this work, and the latter is determined by means of different models:

2.1.2. The Smagorinsky Model

For most of the eddy-viscosity models, the eddy-viscosity can be written in the general formulation:

$$\nu_{sgs} = C_s^2 \Delta^2 \overline{\mathbf{OP}}(x, t)$$

Where C_s is the constant of the model used in the study, the operator Δ presents the sub-grid characteristic length scale, the $\overline{\mathbf{OP}}$ is another operator of space and time which is defined from the resolved fields as below:

$$\overline{\mathbf{OP}} = \sqrt{2 \bar{S}_{ij} \bar{S}_{ij}}$$

The \bar{S}_{ij} presents the filtered strain rate tensor ; $\bar{S}_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}_j}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} \right)$, the constant C_s is usually between 0.1 and 0.2, and in this study $C_s = 0.17$.

2.1.3. The Dynamic Smagorinsky Model

Regarding the Dynamic Smagorinsky model, another test filter bigger than the first one is used in the model ($\hat{\Delta} = 2\Delta$). The eddy-viscosity is expressed as the standard form as the formulation below,

$$\nu_t = C_d^2 \Delta^2 \overline{\mathbf{OP}}(x, t)$$

Where C_d^2 , computed dynamically from the resolved scales ($C_d = C_d(x, y, z, t)$), has the following expression:

$$C_d^2 = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\langle L_{ij} M_{ij} \rangle^+}{M_{ij} M_{ij}}$$

Where L_{ij} is the Leonard tensor with $L_{ij} = \widehat{u_i u_j} - \widehat{u_i} \widehat{u_j}$ and, $M_{ij} = \widehat{\Delta^2 \overline{\mathbf{OP}} \widehat{S}_{ij}} - (\widehat{\Delta^2 \overline{\mathbf{OP}} \widehat{S}_{ij}})$. For more details the reader is referred to the [16].

2.1.4. WALE: Wall-Adapting Local Eddy viscosity

The WALE model [17] is based on the square of the velocity gradient tensor, which takes into account the shear stress tensor as well as the rotation tensor. For turbulent SGS eddy-viscosity ν_t is determined as following

$$\nu_t = (C_w \Delta)^2 \frac{(S_{ij}^d S_{ij}^d)^{3/2}}{(\bar{S}_{ij} \bar{S}_{ij})^{5/2} + (S_{ij}^d S_{ij}^d)^{5/4}} \quad (6)$$

The C_w presents the dimensionless constant of WALE model where $C_w = 0,325$ in this work.

The S_{ij}^d is defined as the traceless symmetric part of the square of the velocity gradient tensor which has the following expression:

$$S_{ij}^d = \frac{1}{2} \left(\left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}_j}{\partial x_i} \right)^2 \right) - \frac{1}{3} \sigma_{ij} \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}_k}{\partial x_k} \right)^2$$

WALE model is used in this study with Spalding law of the wall function since that the configuration investigated is considered as bounded burner. This function can be used to provide near-wall boundary conditions for the momentum and turbulence transport equations, rather than conditions at the wall itself, so that the viscous sublayer does not have to be resolved and the need for a very fine mesh is circumvented. [18]

2.1.5. The One-Eq Eddy viscosity Model

The one Eq Eddy viscosity model used in this work was implemented using the Van-Driest wall damping procedure in order to damp various physical quantities in the neighborhood of a wall, in particular the viscosity.

The value of the turbulent model constant is $C_k = 0.094$.

3. Experimental Setup

The measurements were taken in the Oxyfuel test combustion chamber in the Reactive Flows and Diagnostics laboratories; Figure.3. The nozzle of the complex swirl burner consists of a bluff body surrounded by two annular orifices; the inner one provides the partially premixed fuel-oxygen (P) and the swirled injectors presenting the secondary annular provide the oxidizer. The swirled part of the burner is composed of 4 straight injectors (S_1) and another 45° angled ones (S_2). The cross section of the combustor is 420x420mm² and the length is 600mm. For the outlet of the burner, the coflow is provided by an annular orifice placed close to the wall (T). Many more other details are described clearly in Samim et al [13].

Regarding the RTD measurements, the injection of the fluid elements as passive scalar which is the natural gas in this study was done in pulse input; this amount of the fluid was suddenly injected in one shot entering the burner through its primary inlet. The outlet concentration is then measured as a function of time, and the curves obtained of concentration–time at the outlet will guide us to define the residence time distribution.

4. Results and Discussion:

4.1. LES

For the case under study, only a coarse grid was used for the numerical simulation. The profiles of the calculated axial values for mean velocities are shown in the associated figure, Figure.5 where the comparison between the numerical and the measured velocities present a good quantitative agreement for different levels of the burner, especially close to the diffuser, in this part of the combustor chamber the integral time lengths and the turbulent structures are both small enough to be well detected by an averaging procedure of 5s physical time which is the

necessary time for all the particles getting through the chamber. Regarding the peak positions for the mean velocity, their maximum amplitude is of around 7,5m s. They are highest in the chamber middle and decreasing in radial and in downstream direction. The positions of the maximum velocities are constant for the first level where the results are sampled and change outwards in radial direction for the downstream levels; here the width of the axial velocities profiles is increasing where the gradient of the velocity is large, and that is due to the presence of the shear layers in such locations.

4.2. Residence Time Distribution

The residence time distribution function and its characterization, based on the Large Eddy Simulation, are evaluated and the results are discussed in this section. The Figure.6 can show the reader how the passive scalar is propagating temporally in term of concentration from $t=0.005s$ to $t=5s$ presented at an axial slice through the domain. The last 3 times show the mixing state of the fuel and the oxidizer after approximately the mean residence time of 2s.

The normalized concentration shown in the Figure.7 presents in fact the comparison of the cumulative residence time distribution $F(t)$ between experimental and numerical measurements observed at two different height positions ($x = [58, 575]$) in order of time within the same time interval. The concentration has been captured using 4 different sub-grid LES models while the simulation as described in details in the Large Eddy Simulation models part of this paper. In comparison with the experimental results, the agreement is slightly accepted since the time of simulation needs to be more extended for more averaging. We can see a difference between the different models calculations from $t=0s$ till $t=2s$ in order to reach the mean value of the measured concentration values, however the values obtained with WALE still in more good agreement with the experimental concentration than other sub-grid models.

According to Figure.8 which presents the comparison of RTD calculations obtained using different LES models, the mean residence time is determined from the profile of cumulative residence time distribution function $F(t)$ amounting to 4 different values between 2,18s and 2,60s.

8. Conclusion

The purpose of the current study is to compare different SGS modelling strategies regarding their influence on the determination of the residence time distribution of the CH₄ elements as passive scalar, in a complex Oxyfuel combustor.

For the first part of the paper, the LES models were compared to experimental data in order to validate the first and second order statistics results which were both in good agreement. And, regarding the residence time distribution analysis which was studied using the coarse grid oh the configuration, the first part of the study showed the temporal variation of the passive scalar compared to the experimental data and using 4 LES models, where the WALE model had so far a good agreement with the real normalized concentration values. For the second part, the RTD was defined based on the variation of the normalized concentration at the outlet of the burner where values provided by the WALE modeling strategy were again the closest to experimental outlet concentration.

The influence of the different models still need to be more investigated in the reactive, case where more other parameters should be taken into consideration, and this presents the outlook of the current study.

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Tables and figures

Tab1: The flow field initial condition

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Value</i>	<i>Units</i>
v	1.513 10⁻⁵	(m²/s)
Sc/Sct	0.714	---
V(P)	13.182	m/s
V(S1)	5.230	m/s
V(S2)	15.008	m/s
V(T)	1.717	m/s

Figure 1: Numerical Grid of the combustor under study

Figure 2: Grid of the swirled injectors

Figure 3: Experimental setup: combustion chamber with different flow injectors

Figure 4: RTD measurements

Figure 5: Comparison with the experimental data of the normalized concentration of the CH₄ just after the injection level using different SGS models

Figure 6: Temporal variation of the concentration of the passive scalar within the unsteady turbulent mixing field

Figure 7: Comparison with the experimental data of the normalized concentration of the CH₄ just after the injection level and at using different SGS models

Figure 8: Comparison of Cumulative residence time distribution function $F(t)$ and RTD calculations of different LES models